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History of Collembola research in Belarus with checklist

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Abstract. A comprehensive overview of the history of Collembola research and an annotated checklist of species in Belarus is presented. The class Collembola belongs to one of the least studied groups of invertebrates. At present, 113 species (4 orders and 15 families) have been identified in Belarus according to literary sources, eight of which require confirmation, 11 taxa were not identified to species. Furthermore, at least 125 additional springtail species can potentially be identified.

Key words: springtails, fauna, research history, checklist, Belarus.

История исследования Collembola в Беларуси со списком видов

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Резюме. Приведены сведения об истории изучения ногохвосток и аннотированный список видов Беларуси. Класс Collembola относится к одной из самых малоизученных групп беспозвоночных. В настоящее время по литературным источникам в Беларуси констатировано 113 видов (из 4 отрядов и 15 семейств), для восьми из них требуется подтверждение, 11 таксонов не определены до вида. Потенциально возможно выявление еще более чем 125 видов ногохвосток.

Ключевые слова: ногохвостки, фауна, история изучения, список видов, Беларусь.

History of the study

Collembola belongs to one of the least studied groups of invertebrates in the Republic of Belarus [Khot'ko et al., 1982; Buřmachiu, 2010]. According to some researchers, the springtail fauna consists of only 15 species [Burko, Lopatin, 2001; Lopatin, 2004]. In subsequent articles, 61 species of springtails were identified in Belarus [Buřmachiu, 2010; Borodin, 2013; Ryzhaya, 2014]. The purpose of this work is to analyze scientific publications to study the history of research of the springtail fauna structure in Belarus and to determine the prospects for further investigation.

The water springtail *Podura aquatica* Linnaeus, 1758 was firstly recorded for Belarus by Solovyov [1926] in a sample of water from Horki (Mogilev Region). The first significant records about the springtail fauna of Belarus were made in 1947 in the works of Jan W. Stach. The records were based on the samples collected on the territory of present-day Brest Region by M. Znamierowska in 1924 [Stach, 1960], by K. Traaczewski in 1929 and 1932 [Stach, 1947, 1949a, 1951, 1954, 1956, 1957, 1960, 1963], and by F. Krasnodębski in 1936 [Stach, 1947], on the samples collected on the territory of present-day Grodno Region by J. Průffer in 1922 and 1930 [Stach, 1960] and by Prof. Federowicz in 1926 [Stach, 1956], as well as on the samples collected by S. Feliksiak in 1924, 1929–1932 on the territory of present-day Brest and Grodno regions [Stach, 1947, 1949a, 1949b (?)] (the record does not allow

to determine whether the material was collected from the Belarusian or Polish part of Belovezhskaya Pushcha), 1951, 1957].

Stach's papers provide an accurate annotated information about springtails supplemented with georeferences and some comments on the biological and ecological features of the identified species. Thus, an interesting discovery was made by F. Krasnodębski in Pinsk on the Pina River at a temperature of –22 °C on 25 January 1936 at 1:00 p.m. He discovered a group of *Isotoma viridis* (Bourlet, 1839) crawling on snow and ice [Stach, 1947]. Stach recorded 41 species from nine families and three orders found on the territory of Belarus for the first time. A number of springtail records from the works of J.W. Stach were also mentioned in the works of Grinbergs [1960] and Martynova [1964a, b].

There are other faunistic works that also contain the Collembola records on the territory of Belarus. Kipenvarlits [1961] discovered four species: *Entomobrya marginata* Tullberg, 1871, *Ceratophysella armata* Nicolet, 1842, *Onychiurus fimetarius* Linnaeus, 1758, *Stenaphorura quadrispina* Börner, 1901 (from four families and two orders). Radzymovsky and Polishchuk [1970] recorded in Belarus *Proisotoma ripicola* Linnaniemi, 1912.

Further studies were continued by Nataliya A. Kuznetsova. Together with co-authors she provided information on springtails of Vitebsk Region [Kuznetsova, 1984, 1988, 2002; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995; Chernov et

al., 2010]. In general, N.A. Kuznetsova recorded 46 species (from 11 families and four orders) for the Belarusian fauna for the first time.

A number of important faunistic records were made in the 80–90s of the 20th century. Molodova [1986] registered *Pogonognathellus longicornis* (Müller, 1776) (verified by M.P. Potapov and I.P. Vtorov) in Gomel Region. Vetrava [1986] recorded *Coecobrya tenebricosa* (Folsom, 1902) and *Entomobryoides purpurascens* (Packard, 1872) for the territory of Belarus, but the collector and locality were not specified. Potapov [1991] published new faunistic data on *Parisotoma ekmani* (Fjellberg, 1977). Two species (*Schoettella ununguiculata* (Tullberg, 1869) and *Willemia intermedia* (Mills, 1934)) from one family and one order were added to the key to springtails of the fauna of Russia and neighboring countries [Babenko et al., 1994], but also without exact locality in Belarus.

Another significant study of springtails in Belarus was made by Galina N. Buşmachi. The research was conducted within a joint scientific project between Belarus and Moldova “Insect Biodiversity (Insecta: Collembola, Coleoptera, Lepidoptera) of the Coastal Areas of River Ecosystems in Belarus and Moldova in a Comparative Aspect” (2008–2010). The results of this project were summarized by Buşmachi [2010]. Buşmachi’s work contains all available information on the springtail fauna of Belarus, including new faunistic records. Moreover, she carried out studies of the Collembola species composition in coastal ecosystems of Belarus (Vitebsk, Brest and Gomel regions). Buşmachi [2010] firstly recorded for Belarus seven springtail species from three families and one order.

Furthermore, a lot of data on springtails were published by Moroz with co-authors [Moroz et al., 2002a, b, 2004a, b, 2005, 2007, 2008, 2012, 2013b, c, d, 2014, 2016, 2017a, b, c, 2018a, b, c, d, 2022; Moroz, Maksimenkov, 2006; Moroz, 2012, 2013a, b, c, 2015, 2016, 2018; Moroz, Laenko, 2013; Tishchikov et al., 2013; Moroz, Vezhnavets, 2015, 2019; Moroz, Lipinskaya, 2017]. *Lepidocyrtus lanuginosus* Linnaeus, 1788 was firstly recorded on the territory of Belarus [Tishchikov et al., 2013], as well as *Deuterostomothrus* sp. [Moroz et al., 2013b].

Willemia scandinavica Stach, 1949 was mentioned for Belarus by Kahrarian [2014] with reference to “Synopses on Palaearctic Collembola” [Thibaud et al., 2004].

Fauna Europaea database [Fjellberg et al., 2013] contains 38 species of collembolans recorded for Belarus, four of which have not been mentioned for the country in other scientific publications: *Entomobrya muscorum* (Nicolet, 1842), *Pseudosinella zygophora* (Schille, 1908), *Ballistura tuberculata* (Stach, 1947), *Morulina gigantea* (Tullberg, 1877).

Orchesella villosa (Linnaeus, 1767) was mentioned for the first time as a representative of the fauna of Belarus in the Global Biodiversity Information Facility [GBIF.org, 2023]. The data presented in the GBIF publication [Borodin, Krasouski, 2020] were previously published by Borodin and Tsinkevich [2016a, b].

Coecobrya tenebricosa Folsom, 1902 and *Desoria olivacea* (Tullberg, 1871) were mentioned in scientific works [Kuznetsova, 1984; Antipov et al., 1986, 1989], but require confirmation.

Other scientific publications reproduce information from earlier sources [Vetrava, 1983a, b, c, 1984, 1986; Chumakov, 1985; Ślawska, Ślawaki, 2009; Fiera, Weiner, 2016; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a, b; Skarżyński, 2019; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020].

The collection of the Siberian Zoological Museum confirmed the discovery of three species, *Isotomurus maculatus* (Schäffer, 1896), *Friesea mirabilis* (Tullberg, 1871), *Micranurida pygmaea* Börner, 1901, in Belarus [Berezina, 2002].

We did not find any information about the history of the formation of the collembolan fauna of Belarus. Only Perkovsky [2017] mentioned an inclusion of a representative of the order Symphypleona in Eocene Rovno amber found in the surroundings of Rechitsa (Brest Region, Stolín District, left bank of the Goryn River, 7 km from the Ukraine border).

In fact, the complete analysis of all available literary sources allowed to expand the checklist up to 113 species (including 8 unconfirmed species). For comparison, more than 130 Collembola species are known in the European part of Russia [Grinbergs, 1960; Babenko et al., 1994], 197 species in Latvia [Juceviča, 2003], 146 species in Lithuania [Grendienė, Rimšaitė, 2009; Grendienė, 2010], 441 species (including 31 unconfirmed species) in Poland [Skarżyński et al., 2002; Ślawska, Ślawaki, 2009], 527 species (including 90 unconfirmed species) in Ukraine [Kaprus et al., 2004, 2006]. Taking into account the number of species from neighboring regions, the potential for studying this group is huge considering that the Collembola fauna on the territory of Belarus is estimated to be at least 238 species [Ulrich, Fiera, 2009].

Material and methods

This work contains only exact records of springtail species on the territory of Belarus.

The subfamilies are listed alphabetically along with the genera and species within each subfamily. Question marks indicate the information that requires confirmation.

The names of the Collembola species in Antipov et al. [1986, 1989] are given in Russian, so specialized books were used to accurately translate the names of species into Latin [Striganova, Zakharov, 2000; Birg, Snitko, 2001; Ümüt, 2018].

Systematic position and synonymy are given according to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility and scientific publications [Janssens, Christiansen, 2011; Hopkin, 2014; Potapov et al., 2021; Collembola, 2023].

Checklist of Collembola

Order Entomobryomorpha

Family Entomobryidae

Genus *Coecobrya* Yosii, 1956

(?) *Coecobrya tenebricosa* (Folsom, 1902)

Records for the region. *Sinella caeca*: Vetrava, 1986: 428.

Sinella tenebricosa Mills, 1934: Antipov et al., 1986: 420; Antipov et al., 1989: 422.

Genus *Entomobrya* Rondani, 1861*Entomobrya corticalis* (Nicolet, 1842)

Records for the region. *Entomobrya corticalis* (Nicolet, 1842): Buřmachieu, 2010: 119–120.

Entomobrya corticalis: Stach, 1963: 64; Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Baquero et al., 2014: 1566; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Entomobrya marginata (Tullberg, 1871)

Records for the region. *Entomobrya marginata* (Tullberg, 1871): Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14.

Entomobrya marginata: Kipenvarlits, 1961: 57; Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 40; Buřmachieu, 2010: 121.

(?) *Entomobrya muscorum* (Nicolet, 1842)

Records for the region. Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Entomobrya nivalis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Records for the region. Stach, 1963: 27; Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Vetrava, 1986: 428; Antipov et al., 1986: 420; Kuznetsova, 1988: 33, 36–37; Antipov et al., 1989: 422; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149; Buřmachieu, 2010: 119, 121; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Entomobrya quinquelineata Börner, 1901

Records for the region. *Entomobrya quinquelineata* subsp. *quinquelineata* Börner, 1901: Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Entomobrya quinquelineata: Stach, 1963: 57; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149; Baquero, Jordana, 2008: 4; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Entomobrya superba (Reuter, 1876)

Records for the region. *Entomobrya superba*: Kurachenko, 2008: 133.

Entomobrya superba: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.*Entomobrya xerothermica* Stach, 1963

Records for the region. Buřmachieu, 2010: 119.

Genus *Entomobryoides* Maynard, 1951(?) *Entomobryoides purpurascens* (Packard, 1872)

Records for the region. *Entomobrya myrmecophila*: Vetrava, 1986: 428.

Genus *Lepidocyrtus* Bourlet, 1839*Lepidocyrtus* sp.

Records for the region. Moroz et al., 2007: 102; Moroz, 2013b: 876; Moroz, Laenko, 2013: 79; Moroz et al., 2013b: 92.

Lepidocyrtus curvicollis Bourlet, 1839

Records for the region. Buřmachieu, 2010: 121.

Lepidocyrtus cyaneus Tullberg, 1871

Records for the region. *Lepidocyrtus violaceus* (Geoffroy, 1762): Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Chernov et al., 2010: 564.

Lepidocyrtus cyaneus: Buřmachieu, 2010: 121; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14.

Lepidocyrtus lignorum (Fabricius, 1775)

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 33, 36–37, 39, 40, 42; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149; Buřmachieu, 2010: 121; Chernov et al., 2010: 563; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Lepidocyrtus paradoxus Uzel, 1890

Records for the region. Buřmachieu, 2010: 121; GBIF.org, 2023.

Lepidocyrtus lanuginosus (Linnaeus, 1788)

Records for the region. *Lepidocyrtus rivularis* Bourlet, 1843: Tishchikov et al., 2013: 160.

Lepidocyrtus lanuginosus Gmelin, 1788: Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14.

Lepidocyrtus rivularis Bourlet, 1942: Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14.

Lepidocyrtus lanuginosus: Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.**Genus *Pseudosinella* Schäffer, 1897***Pseudosinella horaki* Rusek, 1985

Records for the region. Chernov et al., 2010: 563.

(?) *Pseudosinella zygochora* (Schille, 1908)

Records for the region. Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Genus *Willowsia* Shoebottom, 1917*Willowsia buski* (Lubbock, 1870)

Records for the region. *Willowsia buskii* Lubbock, 1870: Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14.

Willowsia buski: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149; Buřmachieu, 2010: 121; GBIF.org, 2023.

Family Orchesellidae**Genus *Orchesella* Templeton, 1836***Orchesella cincta* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Records for the region. Stach, 1960: 125; Buřmachieu, 2010: 119; Fjellberg et al., 2013; GBIF.org, 2023.

Orchesella flavescens (Bourlet, 1839)

Records for the region. *Orchesella flavescens* Bourlet, 1839 var. *lateralis*: Stach, 1960: 45.

Orchesella flavescens: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Molodova, 1986: 300–301; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149; Buşmachi, 2010: 119–121; Chernov et al., 2010: 563; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020; GBIF.org, 2023.

Orchesella pulchra Scherbakov, 1898

Records for the region. Buşmachi, 2010: 120–121.

Orchesella spectabilis Tullberg, 1871

Records for the region. Stach, 1960: 53; Buşmachi, 2010: 119–121; Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Orchesella sphagneticola Stach, 1960

Records for the region. Stach, 1960: 132; Potapov, Kremenitsa, 2008: 108, 112; Buşmachi, 2010: 120–121; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14.

Orchesella villosa (Linnaeus, 1767)

Records for the region. GBIF.org, 2023.

Family Tomoceridae

Genus *Pogonognathellus* Paclt, 1944

Pogonognathellus flavescens (Tullberg, 1871)

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 36–37, 42; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149; Buşmachi, 2010: 121; Chernov et al., 2010: 563; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 13; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Pogonognathellus longicornis (Müller, 1776)

Records for the region. *Tomocerus longicornis* Müller, 1776: Molodova, 1986: 300–301; Buşmachi, 2010: 121; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 13.

Genus *Tomocerus* Nicolet, 1842

Tomocerus vulgaris (Tullberg, 1871)

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Buşmachi, 2010: 121; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 13.

Order Neelipleona

Family Neelidae

Genus *Megalothorax* Willem, 1900

Megalothorax minimus Willem, 1900

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 36–37, 39; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Genus *Neelus* Folsom, 1896

Neelus murinus Folsom, 1896

Records for the region. Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Order Poduromorpha

Family Hypogastruridae

Genus *Ceratophysella* Börner, 1932

Ceratophysella armata (Nicolet, 1842)

Records for the region. *Hypogastrura armata* (Nicolet, 1842): Kipenvarlits, 1961: 57.

Ceratophysella armata: Vetrava, 1983b: 60; Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Antipov et al., 1986: 420; Antipov et al., 1989: 422; Martynova, 1964b: 850.

Ceratophysella mosquensis (Becker, 1910)

Records for the region. *Ceratophysella monstrosa* Gisin, 1949: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 42.

Ceratophysella mosquensis: Kuznetsova, 2002: 380.

Ceratophysella scotica (Carpenter et Evans, 1899)

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 42; Babenko et al., 1994: 142; Sławska, Sławski, 2009: 41; Buşmachi, 2010: 118–119; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Skarżyński, 2019: 152; Skarżyński et al., 2021: 12.

Genus *Choreutinula* Paclt, 1944

Choreutinula inermis (Tullberg, 1871)

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a: 13; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Genus *Seira* Lubbock, 1870

Seira squamoornata (Scherbakov, 1898)

Records for the region. Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Genus *Schoettella* Schäffer, 1896

Schoettella ununguiculata (Tullberg, 1869)

Records for the region. Babenko et al., 1994: 197; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Buşmachi, 2010: 118–119; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a: 13; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Genus *Willemia* Börner, 1901

Willemia anophthalma Börner, 1901

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 30, 33, 36–37, 39–40, 42; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Kuznetsova, 2002: 379; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a: 13; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Willemia denisi Mills, 1932

Records for the region. *Willemia aspinata* Stach, 1949: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 36–37, 42.

Willemia denisi: Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a: 13; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Willemia intermedia Mills, 1934

Records for the region. Babenko et al., 1994: 243; Buşmachiu, 2010: 118–119; Fjellberg et al., 2013.

(?) *Willemia scandinavica* Stach, 1949

Record for the region. Kahrarian, 2014: 23.

Genus *Xenylla* Tullberg, 1869

Xenylla sp.

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 33; Buşmachiu, 2010: 120; Chernov et al., 2010: 564.

Xenylla brevicauda Tullberg, 1869

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 36–37, 40; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Kuznetsova, 2002: 377; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a: 13; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Xenylla grisea Axelson, 1900

Records for the region. Stach, 1949a: 225; Grinbergs, 1960: 27; Buşmachiu, 2010: 119.

Family Isotomidae

Genus *Anurophorus* Nicolet, 1842

Anurophorus laricis Nicolet, 1842

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Buşmachiu, 2010: 120–121; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14.

Anurophorus septentrionalis Palissa, 1966

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1988: 30, 33, 36–37, 39–40, 42; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Kuznetsova, 2002: 376–377; Buşmachiu, 2010: 118–119; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Genus *Bagnallella* Salmon, 1951

Bagnallella sp.

Records for the region. Potapov et al., 2021: 170.

Bagnallella ripicola (Linnaniemi, 1912)

Records for the region. *Proisotoma ripicola* Linnaniemi, 1912: Radzymovsky, Polishchuk, 1970: 179; Moroz et al., 2002a: 90; Moroz et al., 2002b: 89; Moroz et al., 2007: 102; Buşmachiu, 2010: 118–119; Moroz, 2013a: 99; Moroz, 2013b: 876; Moroz et al., 2013b: 92; Tishchikov et al., 2013: 160; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Moroz, 2018: 203; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Genus *Ballistura* Börner, 1906

(?) *Ballistura tuberculata* (Stach, 1947)

Records for the region. Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Genus *Desoria* Agassiz et Nicolet, 1841

Desoria hiemalis (Schött, 1893)

Records for the region. *Isotoma hiemalis* Schött, 1893: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 30, 33, 36–37, 39–40, 42; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149.

Desoria hiemalis: Fjellberg et al., 2013; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Desoria blekeni Leinaas, 1980

Records for the region. Buşmachiu, 2010: 120–121; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14.

Desoria divergens (Axelson, 1900)

Records for the region. Chernov et al., 2010: 563.

(?) *Desoria olivacea* (Tullberg, 1871)

Records for the region. *Isotoma gr. olivacea*: Kuznetsova, 1984: 258.

Desoria violacea (Tullberg, 1877)

Records for the region. *Isotoma violacea* Tullberg, 1876: Stach, 1947: 415.

Isotoma neglecta Schäffer: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 42.

Desoria neglecta (Schaeffer, 1900): Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Desoria violacea: Kuznetsova, 2002: 380.

Genus *Folsomia* Willem, 1902

Folsomia fimetarioides (Axelson, 1903)

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.

Folsomia manolachei Bagnall, 1939

Records for the region. Chernov et al., 2010: 563.

Folsomia quadrioculata (Tullberg, 1871)

Records for the region. Stach, 1947: 169; Grinbergs, 1960: 37; Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 30, 33, 36–37, 39, 42; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Kuznetsova, 2002: 376; Buşmachiu, 2010: 119; Chernov et al., 2010: 563; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Genus *Isotoma* Bourlet, 1839

Isotoma sp.

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.

Isotoma riparia (Nicolet, 1842)

Records for the region. Buşmachi, 2010: 120–121.

Isotoma viridis Bourlet, 1839

Records for the region. *Isotoma (Isotoma) viridis* Bourlet, 1838: Grinbergs, 1960: 43.

Isotoma viridis: Stach, 1947: 428; Vetrava, 1983c: 399; Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Antipov et al., 1986: 420; Kuznetsova, 1988: 42; Antipov et al., 1989: 422; Baichorov et al., 2002: 76; Moroz et al., 2002a: 90; Moroz et al., 2004a: 201; Moroz et al., 2005: 101; Moroz, Maksimenkov, 2006: 58; Moroz et al., 2007: 102; Moroz et al., 2008: 44; Buşmachi, 2010: 118–121; Moroz, 2012: 52; Moroz et al., 2012: 159; Moroz, 2013a: 99; Moroz, 2013c: 11; Moroz, Vezhnovets, 2013: 83; Moroz, Laenko, 2013: 79; Moroz et al., 2013b: 92; Moroz et al., 2013c: 107; Moroz et al., 2013d: 71; Tishchikov et al., 2013: 160; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Moroz et al., 2014: 23; Moroz, 2015: 194; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Moroz, 2016: 50; Moroz et al., 2016: 58; Moroz, Lipinskaya, 2017: 34; Moroz et al., 2017c: 70, 72; Moroz, 2018: 203; Moroz et al., 2018a: 16; Moroz et al., 2018c: 75; Moroz et al., 2018b: 404; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Genus *Isotomiella* Bagnall, 1939*Isotomiella minor* (Schäffer, 1896)

Records for the region. Stach, 1947: 303; Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 30, 33, 36–37, 39–40, 42; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Kuznetsova, 2002: 376–377; Buşmachi, 2010: 118–120; Chernov et al., 2010: 563; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Genus *Isotomurus* Börner, 1903*Isotomurus* sp.

Records for the region. Moroz et al., 2013b: 92.

Isotomurus maculatus (Schäffer, 1896)

Records for the region. *Orchesella bifasciata* (Bourlet, 1839): Stach, 1960: 108; Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 40; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149; Buşmachi, 2010: 119–121; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Collection. Berezina [2002].

Isotomurus palustris (Müller, 1776)

Records for the region. *Isotomurus (Isotomurus) palustris* Müller, 1776: Grinbergs, 1960: 46.

Isotomurus palustris: Stach, 1947: 456; Moroz et al., 2007: 102; Buşmachi, 2010: 119–121; Moroz, 2012: 52; Moroz et al., 2012: 159; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Moroz, 2013b: 876; Moroz et al., 2013b: 92; Tishchikov et al., 2013: 160; Moroz, Vezhnovets, 2015: 73; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Moroz et al., 2017a: 49; Moroz et al., 2017c: 70, 72; Moroz, 2018: 203; Moroz et al., 2018c: 75; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Isotomurus stuxbergi (Tullberg, 1877)

Records for the region. *Isotomurus ciliatus* Stach, 1947: Stach, 1947: 479.

Isotomurus (Isotomurus) ciliatus Stach, 1947: Grinbergs, 1960: 45.

Isotomurus ciliatus Stach, 1947: Martynova, 1964a: 75; Buşmachi, 2010: 118–119.

Isotomurus stuxbergi: Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Genus *Pachyotoma* Bagnall, 1949*Pachyotoma crassicauda* (Tullberg, 1871)

Records for the region. *Ballistura crassicauda* Tullberg, 1871: Stach, 1947: 244.

Pachyotoma crassicauda: Grinbergs, 1960: 40; Buşmachi, 2010: 119; Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Genus *Parisotoma* Bagnall, 1940*Parisotoma ekmani* (Fjellberg, 1977)

Records for the region. *Isotoma ekmani* Fjellberg, 1977: Potapov, 1991: 276.

Parisotoma ekmani: Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Parisotoma notabilis (Schäffer, 1896)

Records for the region. *Isotoma notabilis* Schäffer, 1896: Stach, 1947: 378; Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 30, 33, 36–37, 39; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Kuznetsova, 2002: 376–377; Kurachenko, 2008: 133.

Isotoma (Isotoma) notabilis Schäffer, 1896: Grinbergs, 1960: 42.

Parisotoma notabilis: Buşmachi, 2010: 119–120; Chernov et al., 2010: 563; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Genus *Proisotoma* Börner, 1901*Proisotoma minima* (Absolon, 1901)

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.

Proisotoma minuta (Tullberg, 1871)

Records for the region. Stach, 1947: 213; Grinbergs, 1960: 40; Buşmachi, 2010: 119; Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Genus *Subisotoma* Stach, 1947*Subisotoma pusilla* (Schäffer, 1900)

Records for the region. *Subisotoma pusilla* Schäffer, 1896: Buşmachi, 2010: 120.

Subisotoma pusilla: Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016b: 14.

Genus *Vertagopus* Börner, 1906*Vertagopus cinereus* (Nicolet, 1842)

Records for the region. *Vertagopus cinerea*: Kuznetsova, 1984: 258.

Family Neanuridae**Genus *Anurida* Laboulbène, 1865***Anurida granulata* Agrell, 1943**Records for the region.** Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.**Genus *Friesea* von Dalla Torre, 1895***Friesea mirabilis* (Tullberg, 1871)**Records for the region.** *Friesea* (*Friesea*) *mirabilis* Tullberg, 1871: Grinbergs, 1960: 28.*Friesea mirabilis*: Stach, 1949a: 292; Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 36–37; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Buşmachi, 2010: 119; Fjellberg et al., 2013; Fiera, Weiner, 2016: 23; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a: 13; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.**Collection.** Berezina [2002].**Genus *Micranurida* Börner, 1901***Micranurida pygmaea* Börner, 1901**Records for the region.** Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 30, 33, 36–37, 39–40, 42; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a: 13; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.**Collection.** Berezina [2002].**Genus *Morulina* Börner, 1906**(?) *Morulina gigantea* (Tullberg, 1877)**Records for the region.** *Morulina verrucosa* (Börner, 1903): Fjellberg et al., 2013.**Genus *Neanura* MacGillivray, 1893***Neanura muscorum* (Templeton, 1836)**Records for the region.** *Biloba muscorum* Templeton, 1835: Stach, 1951: 45.*Neanura* (*Neanura*) *muscorum* Templeton, 1835: Grinbergs, 1960: 32.*Neanura muscorum*: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 39; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Buşmachi, 2010: 119; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a: 13; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.**Genus *Pseudachorutes* Tullberg, 1871***Pseudachorutes dubius* Krausbauer, 1898**Records for the region.** Stach, 1949b: 103 (?) (the record does not allow to determine whether the material was collected from the Belarusian or Polish part of Belovezhskaya Pushcha); Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148.*Pseudachorutes corticicolus* Schaffer, 1896**Records for the region.** Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.*Pseudachorutes parvulus* Börner, 1901**Records for the region.** Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1984: 39; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148;

Buşmachi, 2010: 120–121; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a: 13; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Pseudachorutes subcrassus Tullberg, 1871**Records for the region.** Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Chernov et al., 2010: 563.**Family Onychiuridae****Genus *Deuteraphorura* Absolon, 1901***Deuteraphorura variabilis* (Stach, 1954)**Records for the region.** *Onychiurus variabilis* Stach, 1954: Stach, 1955: 56.**Genus *Oligaphorura* Bagnall, 1949***Oligaphorura absoloni* (Börner, 1901)**Records for the region.** *Onychiurus absoloni*: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.*Micraphorura absoloni* Börner, 1901: Kuznetsova, 2002: 376; Buşmachi, 2010: 118–119; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a: 13.*Oligaphorura absoloni*: Kuznetsova, 1988: 30, 33, 36–37, 39–40, 42; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.**Genus *Onychiurus* Gervais, 1841***Onychiurus fimetarius* (Linnaeus, 1758)**Records for the region.** Kipenvarlits, 1961: 57; Vetrava, 1983a: 96; Antipov et al., 1986: 420; Antipov et al., 1989: 422.**Genus *Protaphorura* Absolon, 1901***Protaphorura armata* (Tullberg, 1869)**Records for the region.** *Onychiurus armatus* Tullberg, 1869: Stach, 1954: 127; Kipenvarlits, 1961: 57; Antipov et al., 1986: 420; Antipov et al., 1989: 422.*Onychiurus nemoratus* Gisin, 1952: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.*Protaphorura armata*: Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a: 13; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.*Protaphorura nemorata* (Gisin, 1952)**Records for the region.** Kuznetsova, 1988: 40.*Protaphorura stogovi* Pomorski, 1993**Records for the region.** Kuznetsova, 2002: 379.*Protaphorura subarmata* (Gisin, 1957)**Records for the region.** *Onychiurus subarmatus* Gisin, 1957: Kuznetsova, 1984: 258.*Onychiurus armatus*: Vetrava, 1983a: 96.*Protaphorura subarmata*: Buşmachi, 2010: 120–121; Chernov et al., 2010: 563; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a: 13.

Protaphorura subuliginata (Gisin, 1956)

Records for the region. Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148.

Genus Xenyllodes Axelson, 1903

Xenyllodes armatus Axelson, 1903

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 42; Kuznetsova, 2002: 380.

Family Poduridae

Genus Podura Linnaeus, 1758

Podura sp.

Records for the region. *Hypogastrura* Bagnall, 1940: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.

Podura aquatica Linnaeus, 1758

Records for the region. Solovyov, 1926: 41; Shalapenok, 1964: 198; Radzymovsky, Polishchuk, 1970: 179; Vetrava, 1984: 448; Antipov et al., 1986: 420; Antipov et al., 1989: 422; Baichorov et al., 2002: 76; Moroz et al., 2002a: 90; Moroz et al., 2002b: 89, 92; Moroz et al., 2004a: 200; Moroz et al., 2005: 101; Moroz, Maksimenkov, 2006: 58; Moroz et al., 2007: 102; Moroz et al., 2008: 44; Buşmachi, 2010: 118–119; Moroz, 2013b: 876; Moroz, 2013c: 11; Moroz, Laenko, 2013: 79; Moroz et al., 2013a: 97; Moroz et al., 2013b: 92; Tishchikov et al., 2013: 160; Moroz et al., 2014: 23; Ryzhaya, 2014: 377; Moroz, Vezhnovets, 2015: 73; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a: 13; Moroz et al., 2016: 58; Moroz, Lipinskaya, 2017: 34; Moroz et al., 2017a: 49; Moroz et al., 2017b: 54; Moroz et al., 2017c: 70, 72; Moroz, 2018: 203; Moroz et al., 2018c: 75; Moroz et al., 2018d: 84; Moroz, Vezhnovets, 2019: 67; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Family Tullbergiidae

Genus Mesaphorura Börner, 1901

Mesaphorura sp.

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1988: 30, 33, 36–37, 39–40, 42; Chernov et al., 2010: 564.

Mesaphorura macrochaeta Rusek, 1976

Records for the region. *Tullbergia krausbaueri* Greenslade, 1992: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.

Mesaphorura krausbaueri: Kurachenko, 2008: 133.

Mesaphorura macrochaeta: Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 148; Kuznetsova, 2002: 376; Buşmachi, 2010: 118–119; Borodin, Tsinkevich, 2016a: 13; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Mesaphorura sylvatica (Rusek, 1971)

Records for the region. *Tullbergia sylvatica* Rusek, 1971: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.

Genus Stenaphorura Absolon, 1900

Stenaphorura quadripina Börner, 1901

Records for the region. *Tullbergia quadripina* (Börner, 1901): Kipenvarlits, 1961: 57.

Order Symphypleona

Family Arrhopalitidae

Genus Pygmarrhopalites Vargovitsh, 2009

Pygmarrhopalites benitus (Folsom, 1896)

Records for the region. *Arrhopalites principalis* Stach, 1945: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 42.

Pygmarrhopalites cochlearifer (Gisin, 1947)

Records for the region. *Arrhopalites cochlearifer* Gisin, 1947: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149.

Pygmarrhopalites secundarius (Gisin, 1958)

Records for the region. *Arrhopalites secundarius* Gisin, 1958: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 42; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149.

Family Bourletiellidae

Genus Bourletiella Banks, 1899

Bourletiella hortensis (Fitch, 1863)

Records for the region. *Bourletiella (Bourletiella) hortensis* Fitch, 1863: Grinbergs, 1960: 59.

Sminthurus pruinosus: Chumakov, 1985: 71.

Bourletiella hortensis: Stach, 1956: 153; Buşmachi, 2010: 120.

Genus Deuterosminthurus Börner, 1901

Deuterosminthurus sp.

Records for the region. Moroz et al., 2013b: 92.

Genus Fasciosminthurus Gisin, 1960

Fasciosminthurus circumfasciatus (Stach, 1956)

Records for the region. *Deuterosminthurus circumfasciatus* Stach, 1956: Stach, 1956: 178; Buşmachi, 2010: 120.

Bourletiella (Bourletiella) circumfasciata Stach, 1956: Grinbergs, 1960: 59.

Fasciosminthurus circumfasciatus: Martynova, 1964a: 97; Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Genus Heterosminthurus Stach, 1955

Heterosminthurus sp.

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.

Heterosminthurus insignis (Reuter, 1876)

Records for the region. *Bourletiella (Heterosminthurus) insignis* Reuter, 1876: Grinbergs, 1960: 58.

Heterosminthurus insignis Reuter, 1899: Stach, 1956: 200; Buşmachi, 2010: 120.

Heterosminthurus insignis: Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Heterosminthurus linnaniemii (Stach, 1920)

Records for the region. *Heterosminthurus linnaniemii* Stach, 1919: Stach, 1956: 189.

Bourletiella (Heterosminthurus) linnaniemi Stach, 1919: Grinbergs, 1960: 59.

Heterosminthurus linnaniemi Stach, 1920: Buşmachi, 2010: 120.

Heterosminthurus linnaniemii: Martynova, 1964a: 97; Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Heterosminthurus novemlineatus (Tullberg, 1871)

Records for the region. *Heterosminthurus novemlineatus* var. *pilosicauda* Stach, 1956: Stach, 1956: 196–197.

Bourletiella (Heterosminthurus) novemlineata Tullberg, 1871: Grinbergs, 1960: 58.

Bourletiella (Heterosminthurus) novemlineata var. *malopigmentata* Stach, 1956: Grinbergs, 1960: 58.

Deuterosminthurus novemlineatus (Tullberg, 1929): Moroz, Maksimenkov, 2006: 58; Moroz, Laenko, 2013: 79.

Heterosminthurus novemlineatus: Buşmachi, 2010: 120; Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Family Dicyrtomidae

Genus *Dicyrtoma* Bourlet, 1842

Dicyrtoma fusca (Lubbock, 1873)

Records for the region. *Dicyrtoma fusca* Lucas, 1849 f. *principalis*: Stach, 1957: 70.

Dicyrtoma fusca Lucas, 1849: Grinbergs, 1960: 62.

Dicyrtoma fusca: Buşmachi, 2010: 120; GBIF.org, 2023.

Genus *Dicyrtomina* Börner, 1903

Dicyrtomina minuta (Fabricius, 1783)

Records for the region. *Dicyrtomina minuta* Fabricius, 1783 f. *principalis*: Stach, 1957: 47.

Dicyrtoma minuta Fabricius, 1783: Grinbergs, 1960: 62.

Dicyrtomina minuta subsp. *minuta* (Fabricius, 1783): Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Dicyrtomina minuta: Buşmachi, 2010: 120–121; Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Genus *Ptenothrix* Börner, 1906

Ptenothrix atra (Linnaeus, 1758)

Records for the region. *Ptenothrix atra* Linnaeus, 1758: Stach, 1957: 90; Buşmachi, 2010: 120.

Dicyrtoma atra Linnaeus, 1758: Grinbergs, 1960: 63.

Ptenothrix atra: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Kuznetsova, 1988: 42; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149; Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Ptenothrix leucostrigata Stach, 1957

Records for the region. *Ptenothrix leucostrigata* Stach, 1957: Buşmachi, 2010: 120.

Ptenothrix leucostrigata: Stach, 1957: 101; Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Family Katiannidae

Genus *Sminthurinus* Börner, 1901

Sminthurinus aureus (Lubbock, 1862)

Records for the region. Chernov et al., 2010: 564.

Sminthurinus domesticus Gisin, 1963

Records for the region. *Sminthurinus niger* Gisin, 1963: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.

Sminthurinus igniceps Reuter, 1881

Records for the region. *Sminthurinus ignipes* Reuter, 1881: Grinbergs, 1960: 58.

Sminthurinus ignipes Reuter, 1881: Buşmachi, 2010: 120.

Sminthurinus igniceps: Stach, 1956: 114; Martynova, 1964a: 96.

Sminthurinus niger (Lubbock, 1862)

Records for the region. *Sminthurinus niger* Lubbock, 1867: Kuznetsova, 1988: 42.

Family Sminthurididae

Genus *Allacma* Börner, 1906

Allacma fusca (Linnaeus, 1758)

Records for the region. *Sminthurus fuscus* Linnaeus, 1758: Grinbergs, 1960: 62; Molodova, 1986: 300–301.

Sminthurus fuscus Tullberg, 1871: Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.

Allacma fusca: Stach, 1956: 221; Buşmachi, 2010: 120; GBIF.org, 2023.

Genus *Caprainea* Dallai, 1970

Caprainea marginata (Schött, 1893)

Records for the region. Chernov et al., 2010: 564.

Genus *Lipothrix* Börner, 1906

Lipothrix lubbocki (Tullberg, 1872)

Records for the region. *Sphyrotheca lubbocki* Tullberg, 1872: Stach, 1956: 214; Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.

Sminthurus (Sphyrotheca) lubbocki Tullberg, 1872: Grinbergs, 1960: 60.

Lipothrix lubbocki: Kuznetsova, 1988: 40; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149; Buşmachi, 2010: 120; Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Genus *Sminthurides* Börner, 1900

Sminthurides sp.

Records for the region. Radzymovsky, Polishchuk, 1970: 179; Kuznetsova, 1988: 42.

Sminthurides aquaticus (Bourlet, 1843)

Records for the region. *Sminthurides aquatica* (Bourlet, 1843): Moroz et al., 2022: 8.

Figs 1–2. Taxonomic structure of springtails of Belarus.

1 – orders; 2 – families.

Рис. 1–2. Таксономическая структура ногохвосток Беларуси.

1 – отряды; 2 – семейства.

Sminthurides aquaticus: Stach, 1956: 25; Grinbergs, 1960: 55; Radzymovsky, Polishchuk, 1970: 179; Moroz et al., 2002a: 90; Moroz et al., 2004a: 201; Moroz et al., 2005: 100–101; Moroz, Maksimenkov, 2006: 58; Moroz et al., 2013b: 92; Buřmachiu, 2010: 118–119, 121; Tishchikov et al., 2013: 160; Moroz, Laenko, 2013: 79; Moroz et al., 2018c: 75; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Sminthurides malmgreni (Tullberg, 1877)

Records for the region. *Sminthurides malmgreni* Tullberg, 1876: Grinbergs, 1960: 56.

Sminthurides malmgreni: Stach, 1956: 31; Buřmachiu, 2010: 120.

Sminthurides pseudassimilis Stach, 1956

Records for the region. *Sminthurides pseudoassimilis* Stach, 1956: Buřmachiu, 2010: 120.

Sminthurides pseudassimilis: Stach, 1956: 45; Grinbergs, 1960: 56.

Sminthurides schoetti Axelson, 1903

Records for the region. Kuznetsova, 1984: 257.

Genus *Sminthurus* Latreille, 1802

Sminthurus sp.

Records for the region. Antipov et al., 1986: 420; Antipov et al., 1989: 422.

Sminthurus viridis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Records for the region. *Sminthurus* (*Sminthurus*) *viridis* Linnaeus, 1758: Grinbergs, 1960: 60.

Sminthurus viridis: Stach, 1956: 271; Chumakov, 1985: 71; Buřmachiu, 2010: 120; Fjellberg et al., 2013.

Genus *Spatulosminthurus* Betsch et Betsch-Pinot, 1983

Spatulosminthurus flaviceps (Tullberg, 1871)

Records for the region. *Sminthurus flaviceps* Tullberg, 1871: Stach, 1956: 259; Chumakov, 1985: 71.

Sminthurus (*Sminthurus*) *flaviceps* Tullberg, 1871: Grinbergs, 1960: 60.

Spatulosminthurus flaviceps: Buřmachiu, 2010: 119.

Genus *Sphaeridia* Linnaniemi, 1912

Sphaeridia pumilis (Krausbauer, 1898)

Records for the region. *Sminthurides pumilis* Krausbauer, 1898: Grinbergs, 1960: 55.

Sphaeridia pumilis: Stach, 1956: 52; Kuznetsova, 1984: 257; Sterzyńska, Kuznetsova, 1995: 149; Buřmachiu, 2010: 119; Borodin, Krasouski, 2020.

Conclusion

After conducting the analysis of all available scientific publications, a checklist of the species observed on the modern territory of Belarus has been compiled. In total, 113 species of Collembola from 4 orders and 15 families have been recorded (Figs 1, 2). Eleven taxa were not identified to species.

Confirmation is required for the following species: *Coecobrya tenebricosa*, *Willemia scandinavica*, *Desoria olivacea*, *Entomobrya muscorum*, *Entomobryoides purpurascens*, *Ballistura tuberculata*, *Pseudosinella zygophora*, *Morulina gigantea*.

Currently, several species mentioned earlier were identified *sensu lato*, but now they have been separated and consolidated into species-groups. As a result, many early records of springtails are obsolete. At present, the *Isotoma viridis* species-group includes the following species: *I. viridis*, *I. anglicana* Lubbock, 1862, *I. caerulea* Bourlet, 1839 and *I. riparia* [Burkhardt, Filser, 2005], as well as the *Parisotoma notabilis* species-group, including *P. notabilis*, *P. agrelli* (Deboutteville, 1950), *P. reducta* (Rusek, 1984), *P. ekmani*, *P. trichaetosa* Martynova, 1977 [Striuchkova et al., 2022], requires confirmation. Early records of *Lepidocyrtus lignorum* may correspond to the following species within the *lignorum* species-group: *L. lignorum*,

L. lanuginosus, *L. pallidus* Reuter, 1892, *L. violaceus* Lubbock, 1873 [Mateos, Álvarez-Presas, 2022].

At present, the estimated diversity of the Collembola species in Belarus is 47.48% of possibly identified species. Determination of the structure of the Collembola fauna in Belarus requires comprehensive studies in various biotopes and on different types of soils.

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